

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN DIABETES MELLITUS TYPE 2 AND GUT MICROBIOME

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is one of the most common chronic disease. In a number of developing and industrialized countries, diabetes mellitus has become an epidemic and is one of the leading causes of death.

The rapid increase of cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) in the past decades has made it a widespread metabolic disorder. In recent years, an increasing understanding of how our microflora is linked to obesity-related T2DM has provided a new potential target for reducing the risk of T2DM.

The aim of our project is to expand our view on key roles of microflora during the onset and development of T2DM as well as its complications. Our aim was to study 2 groups of people with T2DM and Pre diabetes in order to reveal any gastro-intestinal problems. According to questionnaires, it appeared that patients with diabetes type 2 had 3 or more gastro-intestinal disorders, 72 % had bloating, 16% constipation and 12% diarrhea. Patients with prediabetes had 3 and more intestinal disorders: 56 % had bloating, 23% constipation and 21 % diarrhea.

Despite, multiple studies supporting the importance of gut microbiota in pathophysiology of T2D, the field is in early stage. Currently, we have reached a point in our understanding that some probiotics and related molecular mechanisms may be involved in glucose metabolism related to T2D. Long-term (12 weeks) inclusion of probiotics in the treatment of type 2 diabetes (Lactobacillus rhamnosus- 1.0×10^9 , Lactobacillus casei- 1.0×10^9 , Lactobacillus acidophilus- 1.0×10^9 , Bifidobacterium bifidum- 1.0×10^9) has a significant positive effect on such gastrointestinal complaints as flatulence, diarrhea and the feeling of being full quickly. For patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, it is advisable to take a long time (12 weeks) to be supplied with a probiotic with the following composition: (Lactobacillus rhamnosus- 1.0×10^9 , Lactobacillus casei- 1.0×10^9 , Lactobacillus acidophilus- 1.0×10^9 , Bifidobacterium bifidum- 1.0×10^9) Type 2 diabetics By taking probiotics in patients, glycated hemoglobin improves by 0.24%.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Gut microbiome, Insulinresitense, probiotics.

Diabetes is a chronic disease that occurs either when the pancreas does not produce enough insulin or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin it produces. Hyperglycaemia is a common effect of uncontrolled diabetes and over time leads to serious damage to many of the body's systems, especially the nerves and blood vessels.

Type 2 diabetes, like cardiovascular disease, cancer and chronic respiratory disease, is considered a chronic and noncommunicable disease responsible for 80% of premature deaths globally [10].

As of 2019, there were approximately 463 million cases of diabetes worldwide with an estimated 700 million by the year 2045 if current trends continue despite the variety of pharmacological interventions currently available[10].

Poorly controlled diabetes and metabolic disorders associated with type 2 diabetes such as impaired lipid metabolism, the presence of oxidative stress and hypertension can lead to both microvascular and macrovascular complications. Some microvascular complications of type 2 diabetes that involve small blood vessels include diabetic nephropathy [17] [2] di-

abetic neuropathy and diabetic retinopathy. Conversely, common macrovascular complications that involve large blood vessels include cerebrovascular disease, coronary heart disease and peripheral vascular disease [10].

A plethora of studies have demonstrated a significant association between changes in the composition profile of gut microbiota and development of diabetes. In particular, perturbed *Bacteroidetes/Firmicutes* phylum eubiosis has been linked with increased intestinal permeability, with infiltration of bacteria byproducts through a leaky gut barrier triggering subsequent inflammatory responses characteristic of diabetes [1] [2]. On the other hand, several bacteria have been shown to exert a protective role by decreasing the risk of diabetes development through reduction in proinflammatory markers and maintaining intestinal barrier integrity[16]. For example, *Lactobacillus fermentum*, *plantarum* and *casei*, *Roseburia intestinalis*, *Akkermansia muciniphila* and *Bacteroides fragilis* have all been shown to improve glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity, and suppress proinflammatory cytokines. [5]

Notably, some drugs such as metformin which is commonly used for diabetes treatment have also been shown to alter the composition of the gut microbiota, suggesting that metformin interacts with the gut microbiota through modulation of inflammation, glucose homeostasis, gut permeability and short-chain fatty acid-producing bacteria [11]. Additionally, in patients with diabetes-associated gut dysbiosis, metformin promotes butyrate and propionate production, improving a patient's ability to catabolize amino acids. These changes coupled with increased levels of *Akkermansia muciniphila* in the gut may contribute to the effects of metformin on glucose metabolism [8]. It appears that the metabolic factors associated with chronic low-grade inflammation and oxidative stress, which link gut microbiota dysbiosis and type 2 diabetes, are the same ones that influence the onset and progression of diabetic complications [6]. This relationship gives credence to the concept that modulation of the gut microbiota may be a promising strategy in the management of diabetes and associated complications as presented in the following sections[3][9].

The aim of our study was to study gut microbiota in Georgian people with diabetes type 2 and prediabetes; We developed a questionnaire that contained 10

simple questions (eg, do you suffer from diarrhea, constipation, flatulence, feeling full quickly, etc.. At the initial stage, 132 patients aged 18 to 75 were interviewed, including 87 women and 45 men. Out of 132 patients, 98 patients had type 2 diabetes, and 34 patients had prediabetes with marked insulin resistance.

Patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus were selected according to the level of glycated hemoglobin, in particular, patients were selected who had glycated hemoglobin >7.5%, which indicates a subcompensatory and decompensatory state of diabetes mellitus. 34 patients were selected taking into account the Homa index, all of them had an insulin resistance index higher than normal, but the presence of type 2 diabetes (according to glycated hemoglobin) was ruled out.

Analyzing the results of the survey, it was found that out of 98 patients with type 2 diabetes, 76 patients had 3 or more gastrointestinal complaints, namely flatulence in 72% of cases, constipation in 16%, diarrhea in 12%. The majority of patients with insulin resistance, more specifically 22 out of 34 patients, also had 3 or more complaints. The percentage of complaints was distributed as follows; Flatulence -56%, constipation - 23%, diarrhea -21% see

Picture N1: Gastro-intestinal complains in patients with DM

Picture N2: Gastro-intestinal complains in patients with Prediabetes

Based on the questionnaire, 58 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus with gastrointestinal disturbances were selected, taking into account the inclusion-exclusion criteria, who underwent a study of the intestinal microflora, through a bacteriological examination of the feces.

Based on the questionnaire, 14 patients were selected from the patients with insulin resistance with gastrointestinal disorders, taking into account the inclusion-exclusion criteria, who underwent a study of the intestinal microflora, through a bacteriological study of the feces.

58 patients with type 2 diabetes were included in study group I, and 14 patients with insulin resistance were included in study group II.

12 patients were also selected to form the control group, the control group was compared with the I study group, i.e. patients with type 2 diabetes.

As a result of statistical processing, we obtained the following values of the χ^2 criterion: Diarrhea - $\chi^2=12.093$ Constipation - $\chi^2=44.903$ Fast stools - $\chi^2=27.5$ Heartburn - $\chi^2=9.768$ Flatulence - $\chi^2=39.862$ Nausea - $\chi^2=12.24$.

Statistical research showed that the value of the χ^2 criterion before treatment and after treatment for all indicators $\chi^2 > \chi^2_{0.05,1}$, i.e. The null hypothesis is rejected and the difference between the two samples is plausible.

In the control group where 12 patients were included, we got the following results: diarrhea - $\chi^2=0.202$ constipation - $\chi^2=0$. Fast weight gain - $\chi^2=2.02$ Heartburn - $\chi^2=0$ Flatulence - $\chi^2=0.168$ Nausea - $\chi^2=0.253$

In this group, the null hypothesis is accepted and the difference between the two samples is not significant, as expected.

As for the II research group, we got the following results: Diarrhea - $\chi^2=4.094$ Constipation - $\chi^2=2.489$ Fast stools - $\chi^2=4.762$ Heartburn - $\chi^2=1.167$ Flatulence - $\chi^2=2.489$ Nausea - $\chi^2=1.167$

The value of the χ^2 criterion before treatment and after treatment for the indicators of diarrhea, fast accumulation flatulence $\chi^2 > \chi^2_{0.05,1}$, i.e. The null hypothesis is rejected and the difference between the two samples is plausible. As for the value of the χ^2 criterion for indicators: constipation, heartburn, flatulence and nausea $\chi^2 < \chi^2_{0.05,1}$, that is, the difference between these two samples is not reliable.

The data obtained as a result of the bacteriological examination of feces in the study groups before treatment and after treatment were also statistically processed according to the following indicators: bifidum bacteria, lactic acid bacteria, enterococci, intestinal sticks (typical).

To test the null hypothesis to determine the difference between two samples, the Wilcoxon-Manna-Whitney U-test was used.

Group I, as a result of statistical research, the following values of the U-criterion were obtained: bifidum bacteria - $U=882.5$, lactic acid bacteria - $U=436$, enterococci - $U=938$,

The value of the U criterion according to the table $U_{0.05;58;58}=1384.08$ (95% probability), in all cases it was found that $U < U_{0.05;58;58}$, which confirms that the difference between the two samples (before treatment and after treatment then) is plausible according to each indicator.

Group II As a result of a statistical study, which included 14 patients, the following U-criterion values were obtained: bifidum bacteria - $U=55$, lactic acid bacteria - $U=44.5$, enterococci - $U=55.5$

U criterion value according to the table $U_{0.05;14;14}=55$ (95% probability).

In this group only the condition $U < U_{0.05;14;14}$ is fulfilled for lactic acid bacteria, which confirms that the difference between two samples (before treatment and after treatment) according to this indicator is reliable, while for other indicators the difference between two samples is not reliable.

Consider a control group that includes 12 individuals.

The value of the U criterion according to the table is $U_{0.05;12;12}=37$ (95% probability). Bifidobacterium - $U=65.5$ Lactic acid bacteria - $U=66$ Enterococci - $U=70$.

In all cases $U > U_{0.05;58;58}$, which confirms that the difference between the two samples (before treatment and after treatment) according to each indicator is not reliable.

A comparison of the I group involved in the study and the control group was made according to the following characteristics: diarrhea, constipation, flatulence, heartburn, nausea, rapid stooling. The results are as follows: Diarrhea - $\chi^2=16.594$ Constipation - $\chi^2=18.364$ Fast stools - $\chi^2=15.956$ Heartburn - $\chi^2=9.979$ Flatulence - $\chi^2=14.605$ Nausea - $\chi^2=4.106$

The value of the χ^2 criterion according to the table is $\chi^2_{0.05,1}=3.84$ (95% probability).

As a result of the statistical research, it was determined that the value of the χ^2 criterion for all indicators of the I group and the control group meets the condition: $\chi^2 > \chi^2_{0.05,1}$, i.e. The null hypothesis is rejected and the difference between the two samples is plausible.

Glycated hemoglobin was also evaluated in study group I before and after treatment. The average rate of glycosylated hemoglobin decreased by 0.24%, which means that through the probiotics we used (*Lactobacillus rhamnosus-1.0x10⁹*, *Lactobacillus casei-1.0x10⁹*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus-1.0x10⁹*, *Bifidobacterium bifidum-1.0x10⁹*) within 12 months significantly improved glycated hemoglobin, indicating a positive effect of probiotics for glycemic control in diabetes mellitus.

SPSS statistical program was used for statistical processing of the results. The obtained results are included in the conclusions.

Conclusion: Long-term (12 weeks) inclusion of probiotics in the treatment of type 2 diabetes (*Lactobacillus rhamnosus-1.0x10⁹*, *Lactobacillus casei-1.0x10⁹*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus-1.0x10⁹*, *Bifidobacterium bifidum-1.0x10⁹*) has a significant positive effect on such gastrointestinal complaints as flatulence, diarrhea and the feeling of being full quickly. The improvement of microflora in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus was manifested by a sharp correction of bifidobacteria, lactic acid bacteria. For patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, it is advisable to take a long time (12 weeks) to be supplied with a probiotic with the following composition: (*Lactobacillus rhamnosus-1.0x10⁹*, *Lactobacillus casei-1.0x10⁹*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus-1.0x10⁹*, *Bifidobacterium bifidum-1.0x10⁹*) Type 2 diabetics By taking probiotics in patients, glycated hemoglobin improves by 0.24%.

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